

Temperature tolerance

Rice response to extreme temperatures in Saudi Arabia

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Winter and summer 1976 crops of 36 rices, including cultivars from Africa, Australia, India, IRRI, Japan, Korea, Saudi Arabia, and Taiwan, were observed for their reactions to extremely low and high temperatures (Table 1) at Al-Hassa Oasis, the main rice-growing area in Saudi Arabia.

Low spring temperatures affected the early growth of winter rice, particularly that of indicas, although most recovered eventually. Decreasing fall temperatures appeared not to harm the ripening summer crop. High temperatures during later growing stages of the winter crop damaged only the grain filling of traditional tropical rices and YR lines

from Australia, but not that of japonicas from Japan and Taiwan. Vegetative growth of the summer crop, especially of japonicas, was severely stunted by intense heat and strong sunlight during early growth. Heat stress was also reflected in the low fertility of japonica rices; indicas ripened normally (Table 2). Grain yields (expressed in panicle weight per plant) of the summer crop, except of the tropical rices, were considerably lower than those of the winter crop. The findings suggest that high yielding semidwarf indica and japonica rices can be grown successfully as winter crops in Al-Hassa. For the hot summer crop, the modern rices are apparently not as well adapted as the traditional rices. Marked differences in varietal responses, however, suggest that improved varieties better suited to local conditions could be selected.

Table 1. Average temperature during several growth stages of winter and summer crops, Al-Hassa, Saudi Arabia, 1976.

Growth stage	Temperature (°C)			
	Winter crops		Summer crops	
	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.
Transplanting	11.5	31.4	17.8	46.8
Heading-ripening	16.5–16.4	42.8–46.3	15.9–14.7	45.0–43.2
Average (10 a.m.)	31.4	34.6	38.5	42.3

Table 2. Performance of winter (W) and summer (S) rice crops, Al-Hassa, Saudi Arabia, 1976.

Plant type	Fertility (%)		Panicle weight (g/plant)	
	W	S	W	S
	Indica			
Semidwarf	86.8	87.5	55.8	36.2
Tropical	30.4	87.3	26.8	46.8
YR Line	22.7	35.8	18.6	12.1
Mean	46.6	70.2	33.7	31.7
Japonica				
Japanese	80.8	10.4	44.3	3.0
Ponlai	90.9	37.7	61.5	10.1
Mean	85.9	24.1	52.9	6.6

Adverse soils

Varietal tolerance of rice to iron toxicity in Liberia

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Iron toxicity and associated nutrient disorders of rice occur widely in swamp valleys newly developed for rice in Liberia and in similar regions in other West African countries. Yield reductions of 10 to 90% have been recorded in the affected areas. Symptoms vary, depending on the variety and the type of imbalance. Bronzing of the leaves starting at the tips is characteristic, but orange or yellowing of leaves may occur; stunting may occur, with scanty root production and spikelet sterility.

In 3 years, 1,400 lines have been screened at the Central Agricultural Experiment Station, Suakoko, in an iron-toxic swamp (pH less than 5, organic matter 5%) that is irrigated by seepage water containing a high level of soluble iron. Most lines have been eliminated from further consideration. Gissi 27, a photoperiod-sensitive local variety, has been found to be consistently tolerant. At maximum tillering its leaves contain 560 ppm iron, compared with 1,650 and 1,720 ppm contained in leaves of the susceptible lines IR269-26-3-3-3 and IR589-54-2. Several lines derived from IR2031, IR2053, IR2070, IR2071, IR2153, and IR2688 have been observed to be tolerant. They involve iron-toxicity-tolerant lines (IR20, IR1416-131-5, and CR94-13) in their parentage. Tolerance appears to be heritable. Some lines from Sri Lanka (Dewarederi, BW191, BW196, BG35-2), Indonesia (B 1896-29-4-3-1, B 4596-Pn-132-3-5, B 459-Pn-132-8-1, B 462-CPn-1-3), and Malaysia (2526, Improved Mahsuri) are also tolerant. Screening and crossing of more germ plasm from those entries should help to develop improved iron-toxicity-tolerant varieties. Several dry-land varieties –

LAC 23 (Liberia), Azmil 26 (Philippines), TOS 4020, TOS 3814 (IITA), and IR1476-F5B-13, IR2989-13, and IR2992-27 (IRRI) — also have shown tolerance to iron toxicity.

Line 2526, introduced from Malaysia and derived from the cross Siam 25 x Malinja³, is the most promising of the tolerant cultivars. It is of intermediate height (120 cm), tillers well, and has

long slender grains; it is insensitive to day length and moderately susceptible to blast, leaf scald, and brown spot diseases in Liberia. It is being tested in minikit trials in farmers' fields in Liberia. ❧

Pest management and control

DISEASES

“Empty-head” — a serious rice problem in Taiwan

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“Empty-head” was severe in the second rice crop of 1976 in southern Taiwan, and occurred sporadically in central and northern areas. About 17,000 ha were affected in some major rice-growing areas. The characteristic symptom is abnormally erect panicles with partially filled or completely empty grains in mature plants. Brown or dark-brown spots appear on panicles and grains and, in severe cases, cover most or all of the surface of some grains. The uppermost leaf sheaths of affected plants turn partially or completely brown; upper internodes of stems enclosed by the uppermost leaf sheath are distorted and have a zigzag appearance. Brown stripes or blotches usually appear on the upper portion of the stem.

The sporadic occurrence of “empty-head” has been noticed since 1968 in the Tainan area. Evidence seems to associate it with the rice tarsonemid mite *Steneotarsonemus madecassus* Gutierrez and the sheath-rot fungus *Acrocyndrium oryzae* Sawada, although the frequent use of organoarsenic compounds, leading to a high arsenic content in the paddy soil, is not excluded as a possible cause. S. P. Y. Hsieh, National Chung Hsing University, recently isolated a large number of conidia of *A. oryzae* from the “empty-head” rice plants, and about 97% of the tarsonemid mites carried conidia.

Biological relationships between the mite and the sheath-rot fungus have not been investigated. At present, the mites

are regarded as a primary factor because large numbers were invariably detected inside spikelets, grains, and leaf sheaths. A research team of entomologists, plant pathologists, and pesticide specialists coordinated and supported by the Plant Industry Division, Joint Commission on Rural Reconstruction, currently has work under way at several research institutions and locations on the “empty-head” problem. ❧

Seed transmission of bacterial leaf blight of rice and its treatment

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Several treatments were tested to determine their relative efficacy in eradicating *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Uyeda and Ishiyama) Dowson from infected rice seed.

Seeds collected from a crop severely infected with bacterial leaf blight were treated with hot water, Brestanol, Streptocycline + Ceresan, Agrimycin + Ceresan, and both dry and slurried Streptocycline, HPMTS, RH 893, Vitavax, and Agricultural Terramycin 17. Hot water, HPMTS, and Brestanol seed treatments completely eradicated the pathogen from the infected seed. Brestanol seed treatment, besides being highly effective in eradicating the pathogen, also gave a higher percentage of germination. In general, slurry seed treatments were more effective than dry seed treatments using the same chemicals. The systemicity of Brestanol and HPMTS was tested after seed treatment, and it was found that those chemicals are absorbed and translocated in the seedlings of treated seeds. ❧

Bacterial blight of rice in Pakistan

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Bacterial blight of rice, caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Uyeda and Ishiyama) Dowson, is one of the major diseases of the crop in Asia. However, it has not been reported from Pakistan. During a survey trip in October 1976, we observed the disease on some Basmati varieties grown at the Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Pakistan. Lesions appeared typically water soaked, with wavy margins and grayish white color on infected leaf blades. Lesion length as well as type suggested that the varieties were quite susceptible. Disease incidence in the field was relatively high. When infected leaves were examined microscopically, bacterial ooze streamed from cut edges of the lesions, although inoculations have not yet been made to confirm the pathogenicity. ❧

In vitro effect of certain fungicides and antibiotics against the bacterial leaf blight pathogen

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Thirteen fungicides and six antibiotics were tested for effectiveness against *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Uyeda and Ishiyama) Dowson, the pathogen of bacterial blight of rice. They were tested at 250, 500, and 1,000 ppm.

At all concentrations tried, the fungicides thiram, captan, Vitavax, and Difolatan inhibited the growth of *X. oryzae*. Among the antibiotics, Streptocycline and Chloroamphenicol at all concentrations arrested the growth of the pathogen. ❧